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The Total Availability of Urban Green Space in the Italian Regions

Between 2011 and 2021 it grew on average by 2.29%

Istat calculates the total availability of urban greenery in the Italian regions. The variable is defined as the number of square meters of urban greenery per inhabitant in provincial capitals/metropolitan cities. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2011 and 2021.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the total availability of urban greenery in 2021. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place by value of the total availability of urban greenery with an amount of 319.2 units, followed by Molise with a value of 317, 3 units and from Umbria with 100.3 units. In the middle of the table we find Calabria with a value of 33.33 units, followed by the Marche with a value of 29.8 units, and Abruzzo with an amount of 291 units. Campania closes the ranking with a value of 15.5 units, followed by Sicily with 15.4 units and Puglia with 9.7 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in the total availability of urban greenery between 2011 and 2021. Campania is in first place for the value of the percentage change in the total availability of urban greenery with a value equal to 9.93% corresponding to a change from an amount of 14.1 units up to a value of 15.5 units. Sicily follows with a variation equal to +9.22% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 14.1 units up to a value of 15.4 units. The Marche region is in third place with a value of 7.97% corresponding to a variation from 27.6 units up to a value of 29.8 units. In the middle of the table is Calabria with a value of 5.38% corresponding to a variation from a value of 31.6 units up to a value of 33.3 units. Sardinia follows with a variation equal to +5.29% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 34 units up to a value of 35.8 units. Molise follows with a variation of 3.83% corresponding to a variation from 305.6 units up to 317.3 units. Umbria closes the ranking with a value equal to +1.62% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 98.7 units up to 100.3 units. Lazio follows with a value equal to +0.46% corresponding to a variation from 21.8 units up to 21.9 units. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with a value of -2.41% corresponding to a variation from 327.1 units up to 319.2 units. Between 2011 and 2021 on average the percentage of total availability of urban greenery grew by 2.29%.

The availability of urban greenery in the Italian macro-regions between 2011 and 2021. The availability of urban greenery between 2011 and 2021 grew in all the Italian macro-regions. In particular, it grew in the North with a value of 3.22%, in the North-West with a value of 4.86%, in the North-East with a value of 2.43%, in the Central Italy with a value of at 1.11%, the South with 6.73%, the South with 6.00 and the Islands with 7.82%. We note that the value of the availability of urban greenery has grown especially in the southern regions in percentage terms between 2011 and

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2021 although in absolute terms the value of urban greenery tends to be higher in the northern regions than in the southern regions.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. We choose the solution with k=3 which is suboptimal compared to k=2 since in k=2 there is an excessive polarization of the two clusters. The identified clusters are indicated below:

- Cluster 1: Tuscany, Piedmont, Lazio, Lombardy, Valle d'Aosta, Abruzzo, Marche, Liguria, Sicily, Campania, Calabria, Veneto, Puglia, Sardinia, Emilia-Romagna;
- Cluster 2: Trentino Alto Adige, Molise;
- Cluster 3: Basilicata, Umbria, Friuli Venezia Giulia.

The analysis results in the following ordering of the clusters: C2>C3>C1. Therefore the regions that have the greatest urban greenery are Trentino Alto Adige and Molise. However, there is a great polarization due to the fact that the values of C2 which is the dominant cluster are very high compared to those of the other clusters. In terms of average value, the values of Cluster 2 are approximately 16 times higher than those of Cluster 1 and approximately 4 times higher than those of Cluster 3. Furthermore, it is not possible to identify elements of discrimination between the clusters that are determined on the basis of socio-economic and geographical conditions as the clusters are very heterogeneous from each other.

Conclusions. The value of the availability of urban greenery appears to have grown between 2011 and 2022 by a value equal to 2.29% on average in the Italian regions. However, the availability of urban greenery tends to be higher in the Northern regions than in the Central-Southern regions.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

